

USE OF ACTIVE TEACHING METHODS IN CHEMISTRY LESSONS**Ravshanova Saodat Abduvaliyevna**

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Abstract: This article provides feedback and suggestions from the authors on their active teaching methods, as well as what to look for and how to approach active teaching methods.

Keywords: student, knowledge, ability, skill, qualification, active teaching style.

Introduction

Today, one of the main features of educational standards in the formation of a new generation of new Uzbekistan is the transition from the formation of students' knowledge, abilities and skills to the formation of student competence. Undoubtedly, the transition from teaching knowledge, skills and competence to a competency-based approach requires changing all components of the educational process: content, control methods, and teaching methods. One of the possible ways of changing teaching methods during the transition to a competency-based approach is the use of active teaching methods in the educational process [1].

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The inclusion of active methods in the educational process increases the cognitive activity of students activates, increases their interest and passion, develops the ability to learn independently; provides feedback between students and teachers whenever possible. Researchers of active learning methods note that if more than 22% of the information is not absorbed during the presentation of the lecture, in the business game - up to 90% [2,3].

Active learning techniques:

1. "Chamomile" technique - "Chamomile" consists of six petals, each of which contains a specific type of question. Thus, six petals are six questions [4].

2. "Basket of ideas, concepts, names" technique - you can draw a basket symbol on the blackboard, in which all the things that all students know together about the topic under study are conditionally collected [5].

3. Acceptance "Diamant" - Diamant is a poetic form consisting of seven stanzas, the first and last of which are opposite concepts, useful for working with concepts that are opposite in meaning.

4. "I know", students make a list of what they know or think they know about the given topic. "I want to know" is a description of what children want to know, to arouse interest in new information. After discussing the text (film, etc.), students fill in the third column of the table "I have learned" [6].

5. "Sinkwine" - This is a five-line poem in which the author expresses his attitude to the problem.

6. "Insert" technique - the technique is used in three stages: In the process of reading, students mark the text with icons ("V" - already know; "+" - new; "-" have a different opinion; "?" - do not understand, I have questions) [7].

7. Reception "Zig-zag" - the technique is used to study and arrange a large amount of material. To do this, it is necessary to first divide the text into semantic parts for mutual learning. The number of transitions should correspond to the number of group members [8].

8. "Backpack" technique - reflection technique is often used after studying a large part in class.

9. "Wise owls" party. We give examples of the use of active methods of education. Example: Lesson method: independent work with the help of a textbook. For example, I use the "Wise Owls" technique, in which "What, you didn't expect?" There is a title with a question: pick out information from the text that is unexpected for you because it contradicts your expectations.

Title "Instructive Summary". From what you read, can you draw such conclusions that are important for future life activities? To purposefully form interest and interest in the topic, I use the visualization method - a research chemical experiment. This research method helps to form practical skills, develop the ability to observe, analyze, draw conclusions, and develop creative chemical thinking. For example, when showing the experiment "The interaction of lithium with copper (II) chloride solution", an unexpected situation occurs: instead of the products of the reaction expected by the students, a new metal and a new salt, copper (II) are formed. Iadi An oxide is formed and hydrogen is released. Example: I conducted role-playing lessons with students: "Test of carbon" (showing the value of carbon and its compounds), "Test of ethanol" (showing the secondary meaning of alcohol), "Test of nuclear energy". For this game, the "accused", "defenders" and "members of the court" headed by the chairman of the court were separated from the group of students, the rest of the students were "spectators" in the courtroom. At the beginning of the lesson, students were given a description of the rules of behavior and roles in the "court". Prosecutors had to tell humanity what ICT was "accused of". The defense, accordingly, should have taken the evidence in their favor. The court must judge whether these substances harm humanity or vice versa. 15 minutes were given to prepare for the "test". At the same time, children were allowed to use literature pre-selected by teachers. Here is a rough list of the literature: a chemistry encyclopedia, a large encyclopedic dictionary, chemistry textbooks for grades 8-11, a selection of computer magazines. A major challenge in providing active learning methods is engaging students in ways that match their learning styles. In this case, assign the roles correctly. The "trial" game was held with great interest, both students and teachers liked this lesson. Example: holding a basketball lesson with students of 8-10th grade on the topics "Excursion to the Land of Metals", "Excursion to the Museum of Entertainment Experiences". To conduct this lesson, the teacher prepares several halls of the "virtual" metal museum and several "exhibits" for the museum of entertainment experiments. In addition, the "exhibits" for each hall were chosen to build a coherent story. As such "exhibits", photographs of contributing scientists and engineers, photographs of individual metals, diagrams showing the properties of metals can be used. The "guide" must prepare a coherent story about the proposed exhibits within 5 minutes. 2 "consultants" help him in

preparing the story. Readers choose the main "intrigue" of the story themselves. Example: Eighth graders are interested in doing home laboratory work: Physical and chemical phenomena, making and using indicators at home, growing crystals, separating compounds, purifying water, etc. The results of these works are presented in the form of mini-projects. Example: An excerpt from the chemistry lesson "Catalysts" in the 9th grade. The teacher invites the students to do a small experiment, hydrogen peroxide can stand for a long time and nothing happens to it, but if you add only manganese (IV) oxide, the hydrogen peroxide will decompose. Thus, manganese (IV) oxide acted as a catalyst. He accelerated the reaction. And what happens to this substance. Take the test tube and look down at the manganese oxide "ass". So, catalysts speed up the rate of a chemical reaction, but are not part of the reaction products. Example: 8th grade lesson[11].

Experiment number: 1. A rust-free steel nail is immersed in a test tube with copper sulfate solution. In this case, the surface of the nail rod is covered with a red free copper coating.

Experiment number 2. Soda solution - NaHCO_3 is boiled in an aluminum container. Colorless gas bubbles are released from the surface of the vessels.

Experiment number 3. After the "silver mirror" reaction, a solution of iron (III) chloride FeCl_3 is added to a test tube coated with silver. The silver coating dissolves and a white precipitate forms. Students answer the teacher's question: What do these three experiences have in common? Lesson topic: "Interaction of metals with salt solutions". Example: Excerpt from the 9th grade chemistry lesson "Thermal effect of a chemical reaction". Admission "Non-standard admission to the class".

Universal TRIZ technique aimed at engaging students in active mental activity from the first minutes of the lesson. The teacher starts the lesson with a counterfactual that is difficult to explain based on existing knowledge. On the display table there is a stand with test tubes, pour sulfuric acid with water in one test tube, it will be warm, dissolve ammonium nitrate with water in another test tube - it will be cold. Example: 8th grade lesson. "Surprise" party. It starts with a short story. In a small African country, children were read a story about

a wonderful country where people walk on water. Now look out the window. Don't you and I walk on water? We are so used to water that we do not notice its wonderful properties. The topic of our lesson is "Water is a universal solvent".

CONCLUSION

Thus, the learning process is not an automatic insertion of learning material into the learner's head. This requires intensive mental activity of the child and his personal active participation in this process: explanations and demonstrations by themselves do not give anyone real, concrete knowledge. This can only be achieved through active learning. The task of the teacher is to direct, show the way, but not to give everything ready, to summarize the student's independent work, to point out mistakes.

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